

BRIDGING THE GAP: A COMPREHENSIVE NEEDS ASSESSMENT ON THE NUMERACY AND FINANCIAL LITERACY OF MANGYANS IN SOUTHERN LUZON, PHILIPPINES

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ABSTRACT

Within the rich cultural landscape of the Philippines, the Mangyan communities situated in Oriental Mindoro emerge as a distinctive and dynamic cultural group. Mangyan, as a comprehensive term, encompasses eight unique indigenous groups situated on the island of Mindoro in the southwestern region of Luzon, Philippines. This study focuses on the Mangyan communities in Oriental Mindoro, Philippines, specifically in Panaytayan, Mansalay. Comprising eight distinct indigenous groups, the Mangyans possess unique tribal identities, languages, and cultural practices. Despite their rich heritage, the interconnected and complex modern world presents challenges that require essential tools and knowledge. This study conducted a Needs Assessment on the Numeracy and Financial Literacy of Mangyans in Panaytayan, Oriental Mindoro, recognizing numeracy and financial literacy as pillars for informed decision-making and effective resource management. Data gathered from 150 individuals belonging to the Hanunuo Tribe in the Mangyan community undergoes sorting, tabulation, and interpretation, revealing significant gaps in numeracy skills and financial literacy. Consequently, the researchers proposed an extension program, "NUMFIN-MC: Nurturing Numeracy and Financial Literacy in Mangyan Community," emphasizing a community-centric approach. Collaboration with the Mansalay Local Government Unit, Research and Development Unit, Extension and Public Information Unit, College of Teacher Education, Mathematics Club, and community members is integral to the program's success. The findings underscore the critical need for targeted educational interventions among Mangyan individuals while acknowledging commendable financial literacy. The extension program aims to address these gaps, promoting economic empowerment and comprehensive

financial well-being within the Mangyan community in Panaytayan, Mansalay.

Keywords: *Needs Assessment, Numeracy, Financial Literacy, Mangyans in Oriental Mindoro*

INTRODUCTION

In the Philippines, Mangyan communities in Oriental Mindoro are known to have a unique and vibrant cultural group. As per Mnl.Op Inc (2019), the Mangyan group which is located in the southwestern part of Luzon, is composed of eight distinct indigenous groups. Each of these groups possesses its unique tribal identity, language, and cultural practices. In the Philippine archipelago, Mindoro is known to be the seventh-largest island with a collective name for the eight indigenous groups located in various Mindoro cities, known to have their names, languages, and set of customs, including Iraya, Alangan, Tadyawan, Tau-buid, Bangon, Buhid, Hanunuo, and Ratagnon.

Panaytayan, in Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro, is known to have multiple Mangyan communities, each with its unique set of cultural practices and traditions. Mangyan groups are rich in traditions and heritage and have thrived for generations in the luxurious sceneries of Mindoro. Nevertheless, as our world today becomes gradually interrelated and driven by economic intricacies, it is vital to ensure that every community has the knowledge and tools needed to navigate the challenges of this modern era. This brings the researchers to conduct a study about Needs Assessment on the Numeracy and Financial Literacy of Mangyans in Oriental Mindoro. Numeracy and financial literacy programs may serve as a way of empowering individuals and communities to make informed decisions, manage resources effectively, and plan for the future. While the Mangyans have preserved their cultural identity, they may face unique challenges in accessing and applying numerical and financial concepts in their daily lives.

According to Del Rosario M., 2021 numeracy is the capacity to obtain, use, interpret, and transmit mathematical facts and concepts to participate in and handle the mathematical problems faced in many situations during adult years. For Mangyan individuals, numeracy signifies the ability to acquire, utilize, interpret, and communicate mathematical facts and concepts, essential for engaging in and navigating various mathematical challenges encountered throughout adulthood. This proficiency empowers them to handle practical situations, such as managing finances, conducting trade, and addressing agricultural tasks that require mathematical reasoning. Numeracy allows Mangyan individuals to make informed decisions, interpret quantitative information, and actively participate in their communities, contributing to their overall ability to meet the mathematical demands of adult life.

Pecson, R.R. et al (2019) revealed that financial challenges disproportionately affect economically disadvantaged families, particularly those classified as indigent. Attaining a heightened level of financial literacy proves instrumental for these families in cultivating

effective financial management practices, fostering savings habits, making sound financial decisions, and judiciously investing their resources. Consequently, financial literacy emerges as a crucial life skill that transcends social statuses and demographics. It becomes imperative for individuals and families, irrespective of their background, to acquire financial education.

Indigenous groups may struggle to get access to formal education systems that promote numeracy skills due to isolation and geographic limitations. Basic calculations such as bargaining, purchasing items, and handling cash might be difficult without numeracy abilities. This might result in dependency on others or exploitation in commercial transactions. Empowering indigenous communities to design their numeracy solutions based on local needs and circumstances would make financial literacy training more accessible, equipping people with practical money management skills that they can use every day. Access to education would be a great help for these indigenous communities to cope with everyday living despite educational challenges.

A diverse group of communities embodying rich cultural traditions and a deep connection to the land is known as Mangyan people of the Philippines. According to the findings of Eduardo, J.P. et al. (2021) the global challenge of ensuring access to education for Mangyan community remains a pressing concern. Despite of international initiatives aimed at facilitating educational access for Mangyan community, there is still much room for improvement in implementation in the Philippines. The findings of Mahmudi, A. et al. (2019), show that being financially literate live a successful life in the future which consists of attitudes, knowledge, and financial skills. Additionally, Guhi P. (2019) revealed that mastering fundamental math abilities like counting, comparing, classifying, geometry, and critical thinking lays the essential groundwork for future mathematical proficiency and academic success. These competencies represent a pivotal stage in mathematical advancement that cannot be by passed. Competencies represent a vital phase in mathematical development and are indispensable; they form the prerequisite for acquiring more advanced skills. Students need a solid grasp of these basic skills before progressing to more complex mathematical concepts. The findings of Indefenso, E.E. et al. (2020) revealed that the findings revealed that there is a significant and positive correlation between numeracy and financial literacy. Similarly, it was revealed that a substantial and direct relationship between problem-solving ability and financial literacy exists. Kremer, S. et al. (2021) concluded that in order to enhance their monetary well-being, Indigenous communities need to enhance their financial literacy. Financial literacy is characterized as the extent to which an individual comprehends essential financial principles and has the capacity, as well as the confidence, to navigate personal finances by making prudent short-term decisions and engaging in thoughtful long-term financial planning, all while considering life events and adapting to changing economic conditions. Furthermore, it entails the knowledge and capability to surmount challenges and make sound financial decisions in day-to-day life.

This assessment aims to explore and understand the current state of numeracy and financial literacy within the Mangyan communities of Mansalay. By delving into the specific needs, strengths, and gaps in these areas, we hope to develop targeted

interventions that align with the cultural context of the Mangyans. The ultimate goal is to foster sustainable development, enhance economic resilience, and empower the Mangyan communities to thrive in the face of evolving societal dynamics. This research can also help policymakers and development practitioners construct culturally relevant initiatives to address the economic and financial issues faced by indigenous people in the Philippines.

Research Questions

Generally, this study aims to assess the needs of the selected Mangyan Communities in Panaytayan, Mansalay in terms of numeracy and financial literacy.

Specifically, this study aims to attain the following objectives:

1. Determine the level of proficiency of the selected Mangyan Community in Panaytayan, Mansalay in terms of their knowledge of basic arithmetic.
2. Examine the financial literacy levels among Mangyan individuals by assessing their knowledge and understanding of financial concepts such as budgeting, saving, marketing, and investing.
3. Based on the findings of the study, what intervention program may be proposed?

METHODOLOGY

The present study utilized the descriptive research method to evaluate the needs of the Mangyan community in Panaytayan, Mansalay. As outlined by McCombes, S. (2019), descriptive research seeks to provide precise and systematic descriptions of a population, situation, or phenomenon. In this study, it was employed to describe the level of proficiency in understanding and application of basic mathematical concepts. and assessing their knowledge and understanding of financial concepts such as budgeting, saving, investing, and debt management among the selected Mangyan individuals in Panaytayan, Mansalay.

The research was conducted in Barangay Panaytayan, Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro, which comprises 63 sitios. Four (4) sitios were chosen for the study: Sitio Calibang, Sitio Ether, Sitio Tanawan, and Sitio Sinugbuan, all belonging to the Hanunuo Tribe. Purposive sampling, a method explained by Dovetail Editorial Team (2023), was employed to select participants based on specific characteristics relevant to the research interests. The participant distribution included 75 individuals in Sitio Calibang, 23 in Sitio Ether, 15 in Sitio Tanawan, and 38 in Sitio Sinagbuan.

A researcher-made survey questionnaire served as the primary data collection instrument, designed to gauge the proficiency levels of the selected Mangyan individuals in Barangay Panaytayan, Mansalay. The questionnaire utilized dichotomous scales, prompting respondents to answer with either Yes or No. Using dichotomous scales in this

study offers a practical and effective means of gauging and addressing the immediate needs of the Mangyan population. The intended respondents consisted of 150 Mangyan individuals.

The gathered data underwent sorting, tabulation, and interpretation using descriptive statistics, including frequency count and percentage analysis. Frequency count determined how often a specific response appeared, while percentage analysis established the relationship between respondents answering Yes or No to the entire population. These statistical tools were instrumental in assessing the proficiency levels of arithmetic and financial education among the Mangyan community.

RESULTS

This presents the tabulation and textual representation of data used in the analysis of the research objectives of the study.

1. Level of proficiency of the selected Mangyan Community in Panaytayan, Mansalay in terms of their knowledge of basic arithmetic

Table 1. Level of proficiency of the respondents in terms of their knowledge of basic arithmetic

Statements	YES		NO	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1. I know how to read numbers. <i>Ako ay marunong magbasa ng numero.</i>	46	31%	104	69%
2. I know how to write numbers. <i>Ako ay marunong magsulat ng numero.</i>	39	26%	111	74%
3. I know how to add numbers. <i>Ako ay marunong mag add ng numero.</i>	36	24%	114	76%
4. I know how to subtract numbers. <i>Ako ay marunong mag subtract ng numero.</i>	36	24%	114	76%
5. I know how to multiply numbers. <i>Ako ay marunong mag</i>	27	18%	123	82%

<i>multiply ng numero.</i>				
6. I know how to divide numbers. <i>Ako ay marunong mag divide ng numero.</i>	19	13%	131	87%

The table shows the level of proficiency of the respondents in terms of their knowledge of basic arithmetic.

As shown in the table, item number 1 constitutes 104 individuals, or 69% are non-readers in numbers, while only 46 individuals, or 31% can read numbers. Moving on to item number 2, a total of 111 individuals, comprising 74% are unable to write numbers, while 39 individuals, or 26% can write. In item number 3, it is shown that 114 Mangyan individuals, equivalent to 76% lack knowledge in adding numbers, leaving only 36 individuals, or 24% who possess this skill. Likewise, item number 4 indicates that 114 individuals, or 76% are unfamiliar with subtracting numbers, with only 36 individuals, or 24% having the ability to subtract numbers. Turning to item number 5, the 123 majority of individuals, or 82% lack proficiency in multiplying numbers, while the remaining 27 individuals, or 18% are the sole individuals who can multiply numbers. Finally, in item number 6, it is highlighted that 131 individuals constituting 87% are not proficient in dividing numbers, leaving only 19 individuals, or 13% who possess the skill of division.

2. Financial literacy levels among Mangyan individuals

Table 2. Level of financial literacy among Manggyan individuals

Statements	YES		NO	
	Frequency	Percentage	Frequency	Percentage
1. I know what money looks like. <i>Alam ko ang itsura ng pera.</i>	138	92%	12	8%
2. I sell goods/products. <i>Ako ay nagbebenta ng kalakal.</i>	122	81%	28	19%
3. I know how to give change. <i>Ako ay marunong magsukli.</i>	133	89%	17	11%
4. I know how to calculate capital in business. <i>Ako ay marunong magbilang ng puhunan sa kalakal.</i>	122	81%	28	19%
5. I know how to calculate profit in selling goods.	95	63%	55	37%

<i>Ako ay marunong magbilang ng tinutubo sa pagbebenta ng kalakal.</i>				
6. I save money from business. <i>Ako ay may naiipon galing sa kalakal.</i>	69	46%	81	54%

The table shows the financial literacy levels among Mangyan individuals.

As depicted in the table, item number 1 reveals that 138 individuals, comprising 92% are familiar with the appearance of money while only 12 individuals, or 8% are not. Moving on to item number 2, a significant majority of 122 Mangyan individuals, equivalent to 81%, engaged in selling goods/products, with only 28 individuals, or 19% not involved in such activities. In item number 3, 17 individuals, or 11% lack knowledge of providing change, whereas the majority, totaling 133 individuals, or 89%, are proficient in giving change. However, in item number 4, 122 individuals, or 81%, demonstrated the ability to calculate capital in their business, while only 28 individuals, or 19% did not engage in capital calculation for their business. Regarding the calculation of profit in selling goods, as indicated in item number 5, 95 Mangyan individuals, or 63% performed the calculation, whereas 55 individuals, or 37%, did not calculate their profit. Lastly, in item number 6, 69 individuals, or 46%, have savings from their business, while 81 individuals, or 54%, do not maintain savings.

3. Proposed Intervention Program

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers proposed an extension program entitled: "NUMFIN-MC: Nurturing Numeracy and Financial Literacy in Mangyan Community" aims to equip Mangyan individuals of selected sitios of Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro with fundamental numeracy skills, including addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division, enabling them to perform essential mathematical operations with confidence and enhance financial literacy among Mangyan individuals, providing them with knowledge and skills needed to manage money, save, and make wise financial decisions.

DISCUSSION

Table 1 implies that a significant portion of the Mangyan individuals in Panaytayan possess limited numerical knowledge, as evidenced by the high percentages of individuals who cannot read or write numbers, and who lack basic arithmetic skills such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. Lack access to education due to the distance of schools, leading them to choose not to attend.

According to Eduardo J. et. Al, (2021), access to education for Indigenous people is a global issue. There are several international efforts aimed at providing IPs with access to education, but the Philippines' adherence and implementation of these measures still leave much to be desired. Increased commitment and comprehensive assistance from the Local Government Unit (LGU) would prove advantageous in delivering appropriate education to our Indigenous Peoples (IPs) citizens.

Table 2 implies that the high percentages of individuals familiar with the appearance of money and actively involved in selling goods/products reflect a strong foundation in basic financial concepts and entrepreneurial activities within the community.

Furthermore, the majority's proficiency in providing change and calculating both capital and profit in business indicates a commendable level of financial literacy. These findings revealed the potential for economic empowerment and sustainable financial practices within the Mangyan community in Panaytayan, Mansalay.

However, the data also highlight areas for potential improvement, particularly in terms of individuals not engaged in selling goods/products, lacking knowledge in providing change, and not maintaining savings from business. Educational initiatives and support programs addressing these could contribute to a more comprehensive financial well-being for the community.

It was supported by the findings of Mahmudi, A. et al. (2019), revealed that possessing financial literacy sets the stage for a prosperous future, encompassing attitudes, knowledge, and practical financial skills.

The proposed an extension program entitled: "NUMFIN-MC: Nurturing Numeracy and Financial Literacy in Mangyan Community" also aims to enhance the numeracy skills and financial literacy foundation of the Mangyan community through tailored interventions. The focus will be on implementing specialized numeracy programs designed to address identified gaps in foundational arithmetic operations. To ensure maximum impact, these programs will employ innovative and culturally sensitive teaching methods, tailored to the Mangyan community's unique context.

Simultaneously, the extension program will strengthen the community's financial literacy foundation by introducing initiatives that explore advanced financial concepts. This includes comprehensive modules on savings management, investment strategies, and financial planning. By examining these aspects, the program seeks to empower individuals within the Mangyan community to make well-informed economic decisions, contributing to their overall financial well-being.

The extension program will be characterized by a community-centric approach, involving active collaboration with the Mansalay Local Government Unit, Research and Development Unit, Extension and Public Information Unit, College of Teacher Education, Mathematics Club, and community members. Workshops, interactive sessions, and resource materials will be customized to align with the cultural nuances and preferences

of the Mangyan community in Panaytayan, Mansalay, sustaining relevance and meaningful connection. The program's success will be measured through ongoing assessments and feedback mechanisms of Mangyan individual, allowing for continuous improvement and adaptation to the evolving needs of the community. This extension program aspires to instill lasting positive changes in numeracy skills and financial literacy, fostering empowerment and sustainable economic practices within the Mangyan community in Panaytayan, Mansalay.

Conclusions

The revealed data highlight the critical need for targeted educational interventions among the Mangyan community in Panaytayan, Mansalay as indicated by high percentages of non-readers in numbers, unfamiliar to numbers and limited proficiency in basic arithmetic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. Addressing these areas is crucial for empowering individuals with essential skills for daily life and future opportunities. To highlight the positive side, the community's familiarity with the appearance of money and active involvement in selling goods/products highlight a solid foundation in basic financial concepts and entrepreneurial activities. Moreover, the majority's proficiency in providing change, calculating capital, and managing profits revealed a commendable financial literacy and business insight. While these findings suggest potential for economic empowerment, careful consideration is needed in areas that require improvements, such as engaging more individuals in selling goods/products, enhancing knowledge in providing change and promoting savings from business.

Recommendations

To strengthen the numeracy skills of Mangyan individuals, it is recommended to implement tailored numeracy programs that target the identified gaps in foundational arithmetic operations such as addition, subtraction, multiplication, and division. These programs should go beyond conventional approaches, incorporating culturally sensitive and community-centric teaching methods to ensure increased participation and effectiveness. Simultaneously, the community's financial literacy foundation can be enhanced by introducing initiatives that delve into advanced financial concepts. These efforts should emphasize areas such as investment strategies, savings management, and financial planning to empower individuals to make well-informed economic decisions. Entrepreneurship workshops and support programs play a crucial role in encouraging more community members to participate in selling goods/products. These initiatives offer insights into sustainable business practices, market analysis, and effective financial management, fostering a flourishing business market. To instill a savings culture, programs should be initiated to educate individuals on the sustainable benefits of saving from business profits, incorporating accessible and culturally relevant mechanisms. Collaborative efforts involving Mansalay Local Government Units, educational institutions, and community leaders are crucial for the success of these educational and financial literacy initiatives. This collaborative approach creates a wholistic approach both educational and economic aspects, promoting the comprehensive well-being of the Mangyan community. Regular monitoring and evaluation mechanisms are essential,

ensuring the ongoing success of the implemented programs by assessing impact and identifying areas for continuous improvement. This adaptive strategy enables the community to respond effectively to immediate feedback and evolving needs, fostering sustainable growth and development of Mangyan individuals.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

Prior to conducting this research study, the researchers sought permission from the Local Government Unit of Mansalay, Oriental Mindoro. The researchers informed the participants about the purpose and process of the study. To ensure participant safety, researchers conducted one-on-one interviews, while also observing and ensuring participants' privacy and confidentiality by collecting data through respondents' questionnaire responses. The researchers ensure that the study does no harm to the respondents, and it should be beneficial for it to be worth implementing.

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